

Intent-Based Network Resource Slicing in 6G

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Abstract—The purpose of 6G mobile networks is to automate network resource allocation and support both new and existing 5G vertical services that have diverse Quality of Service (QoS) intent requirements. In this paper, we present an optimization model for an Intent-Based Network (IBN) slicing framework to identify slice intent conflicts by closed-loop evaluation and monitoring. This framework jointly resolves the issue of slice intent conflict detection and resolution by formulating an intent life-cycle optimization problem to handle the slice intent conflicts. We assess the capabilities of each slice to determine any conflicts in slice intent and evaluate the impact of achieving the agreed-upon Service Level Agreement (SLA) objectives (%) for the slices with higher priority that need to be addressed. Based on our findings, this approach successfully meets the SLA target we set for the uRLLC slice but it negatively impacts the performance of eMBB and mMTC slices and degrades their slice capacity.

Index Terms—6G, Intent-Based Management, Intent-Based Network Slicing, QoS, SLA, Intent Closed-loop Handling

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of Sixth Generation (6G) mobile communications promises a revolutionary enhancement in mobile communication by targeting ultra-low latency, massive connectivity, and unprecedented data rates to support different services with considerably varied Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. The main service types are classified by International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [1], Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (uRLLC), and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), each aiming for different intents, which should be carefully explored and addressed by Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) or Digital Service Provider (DSP)¹. The eMBB has to deal with services that have demanding high-bandwidth requirements (*e.g.*, 3D videos) and is thus categorized with the intent to focus on throughput expectations. The uRLLC caters to services needing minimal latency and high reliability (*e.g.*, health care monitoring), thereby, delay or reliability is considered as an intent expectation for this service. Finally, mMTC is for the services with low power and constrained resources devices that require high-connection density, yet maintaining relaxed latency and throughput requirements (*e.g.*, sensors), where the massive connectivity is the primary intent. DSPs must consider these specific intents, respective expectations, and targets set by different customers and verticals. Effectively managing overlapping, diversified, and potentially conflicting intents from various services, such as throughput, interference, delay constraints, reliability, and energy requirements, is an

essential aspect of managing and handling intents in 6G. Different complexities and challenging issues arise when addressing these intents. A critical challenge is intent conflicts which can result from conflicting expectation targets of services within the same intent or among other intents. For example, considering throughput as an intent expectation for eMBB service with a specific target $target_1 =: throughput > threshold_1$ and reliability as an intent expectation for uRLLC service with $target_2 =: Reliability > threshold_2$, and while trying to achieve $target_1$ in eMBB intent, $target_2$ of uRLLC intent could be negatively affected. Hence, the DSP should detect targets that conflict with other intents, and establish a proper policy to handle different intent conflicts to deal with this challenge. The traditional approaches to handling such complexities injected by the intent of different Fifth Generation (5G) services with different QoS intents are inefficient and require new technologies to manage and handle them efficiently. To this aim, various technologies are dealing with these issues. Network Slicing (NS) is among the primary technologies providing on-demand virtual network slices that are customized to various Mobile Virtual Network Operators (MVNOs), network services, verticals, and service requirements [2]–[5]. Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) are two key enablers for NS that create isolated slice resources to fulfill the requirements for services [6]. Various service types, such as eMBB, uRLLC, and mMTC, may have distinct NS requirements. Each NS can be classified into different Network Slice Subnets (NSSs), which consist of Access Network (AN), Transport Network (TN), and Core Network (CN) as defined in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [7]. Indeed each NSS contains distinct sets of NFVs of AN, TN, or CN, and the selection of NFVs varies based on service type. Additionally, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) provides an open-source orchestrator for NS which has been developed based on NFV specification named Open Source MANO (OSM) [8], [9].

Another important technology is the Intent-Based Network (IBN) which provides an abstraction layer that separates the application layer from the underlying infrastructure. Furthermore, IBN simplifies the management and interaction of resources frequently distributed across multiple data centers or located in distinct geographic areas. IBN management and orchestration facilitate a greater level of automation and programmability in networks by enabling the specification of requirements and restrictions in an abstract and technology-independent manner [10], [11]. IBN system automates NS by supplying higher-level configurations from the front-end tool and optimizes network design, deployment, and management

¹Note that, in this work, both terminologies of DSP and MNO refer to the same domain of owners providing services for customers/verticals, hence, hereafter we will use DSP that includes MNO as well.

by aligning with business objectives and User Equipment (UE) intent specified by different verticals. In particular, the primary mission of IBN is intent translation, where it aims to identify the items present in the UE intent and transform them into related network configurations, taking into account the current state of the network [12].

In the literature, different works study IBN network management [13]–[16], where these works have certain limitations to (i) address tailored slice intent types with various QoS intent prerequisites, (ii) ensure that each slice has exposure to ample network resources for fulfilling its intents, and (iii) re-configure and prioritize the most critical slice intents when there are insufficient resources available. Hence, the aim of this study is to present a flexible network paradigm using IBN slicing that can manage the complexity of QoS of intents and resolve existing conflicts of intents. In this work, we propose the optimization framework for IBN slicing, which maximizes the throughput while fulfilling the intent requests respecting the network resource constraints. Our main contributions are summarized as follows:

- We formulate a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) framework for IBN slicing that tackles the complexity of QoS intents by formulating the life-cycle of IBN systems.
- We create isolated and tailored slices based on QoS and profile of UE/service intents, where each slice has distinct intents with agreed Service Level Agreement (SLA) objectives that need to be justified and addressed.
- Each service maps with the corresponding NSSs based on its QoS intents, hence, the network resources of a particular slice may be common or distinct.
- Our proposed framework models slice intent closed-loop management to detect conflicts and resolve existing conflicts of intents by varying SLA thresholds while considering the priorities of slice intents.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The system model includes a network model encompassing AN and CN and the TN that connects CN and RAN elements. Likewise, the UE intent representing the traffic demand with different QoS intents and specific profiles is explained. Finally, the problem statement describes the existing problems and motivation of this work.

A. Network and Demand Model

We consider End-to-End (E2E) network architecture composed of AN, CN, and TN. ANs consist of Distributed Units (DUs), which are positioned in the network edge next to UEs, and Central Unit (CU). The CN is composed of common core Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs), and the TN connects ANs and CN. Our network architecture is denoted by $G = (\mathcal{I}, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{L})$ as a graph. Here, \mathcal{I} represents a superset of CN defined as node 0, n_0 and set of A ANs, \mathcal{V} corresponds to a set of FNs, and \mathcal{L} reflects set of links that connect these elements. In this case, $\mathcal{N} = \{0, 1, \dots, V + A\}$ refers to complete set of nodes where CN is node 0; FNs are denoted by $\mathcal{V} = \{1, \dots, V\}$; and ANs are shown by $\mathcal{A} = \{V + 1, \dots, V + A\}$. Accordingly, $\mathcal{N} = \mathcal{I} \cup \mathcal{V}$. The

set of links, \mathcal{L} , is defined as $\mathcal{L} = \{l_{i,j} : i, j \in \mathcal{N}\}$. Each link $l_{i,j} \in \mathcal{L}$ possesses a capacity of $\omega_{i,j} \geq 0$ (in b/s). As referenced in [17], we assume that the transmitted power per Physical Resource Blocks (PRB) is equal, and we will use a path-loss model that depends on distance [18].

As for demand, we consider a set \mathcal{U} of U UEs, i.e., $\mathcal{U} = \{1, \dots, U\}$ and denote service type $s \in \mathcal{S}$, where $\mathcal{S} = \{1, 2, 3\}$ with different QoS intents. The UEs' intent is characterized by their specific QoS intent profile including the λ_u^s that defines the required data rate of UE u with service type s .

B. Problem Statement

The DSP may receive an UE intent that includes two or more intent expectations. Each intent expectation may consist of several expectation targets. For instance, an intent may have targets on KPIs (*e.g.*, UE throughput target, average Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) target, reliability, *etc.*). On receiving and after analyzing the intent, the DSP may perform the feasibility check to assess whether the intent expectations or expectation targets in one intent are contradicted, *i.e.*, detect conflicts in the intent, that could be conflict within the same intent (inter-conflict) or other intents (intra-conflict), as defined in 3GPP [19]. To this aim, DSPs need to detect UE/service intent conflicts and resolve them in real-time, fulfilling the QoS intent requirements. Note that we focus on intra-conflict detection and resolution and propose an optimization framework that will be discussed in the following section.

III. PROPOSED METHOD: IBN SLICING FORMULATION

Within this concept, we introduce a novel optimization framework formulating the intent life-cycle of UEs/services using NS. Our framework first aims to model intent interface (profiling UE/service intents and mapping them to NSs), then model slice intent fulfillment (including intent translation, and slice intent creation) to create tailored slices based on QoS intents and detect intent conflicts of each slice. Finally, the slice intent assurance module aims to resolve the conflicts by injecting varied agreed SLA objectives.

A. Intent Life-Cycle Modeling

Here in this subsection, we present a novel optimization model for the life-cycle of UE intents. This model covers several aspects of intents, including their arrival and the time they are served and incorporates multiple modularities. We further discuss the specific intents modular and their corresponding translated constraints, where they are then combined to create an E2E optimization model for intent-driven network slicing management.

1) *Intent Interface*: The first module of UE/service intent involves interfacing the intent and profiling the service intents. In principle, the initial stage of this module is to classify the received services based on their intent information, profile service intents, and abstract relevant information. We define service type s based on the profile of received services, accordingly, each UE/service belongs to the list of services

$\mathcal{S} = \{1, 2, 3\}$, where $s = 1$ indicates uRLLC service, $s = 2$ denotes mMTC service, and finally $s = 3$ refers to eMBB service, respectively. We next need to map each service to the corresponding NSS in the network. Accordingly, the mapping of services to NSSs can be represented using a function $f : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{N}$ as follows:

$$f(s) = N_s, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (1)$$

The next step of this module is to create an NSS template for each service taking all functionalities of this module into account, which can be defined as:

$$N_s = \begin{cases} a & \text{if } s = 1 \\ a \cup l_{i,j} \cup n_0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where N_s is creating a customized NSS template based on the profile of each service. Fig. 1 illustrates the IBN slicing architecture and how different slices are provisioned among different layers of the network. For example for $s = 1$ which is uRLLC service, NSS creation will be tailored to meet UE QoS intent, and, accordingly, the uRLLC slice template with the flavor of having resources in the edge side (including Edge Cloud (CU) and Far Edge (DU)) within AN will be created, as *i.e.*, $N_s = a$. For the rest UEs with no critical QoS intents, we instantiate NSS encompassing $N_s = a \cup l_{i,j} \cup n_0$. Note that the AN (a), TN ($l_{i,j}$), and CN resources (n_0) are denoted as $NSS - AN$, $NSS - TN$ and $NSS - CN$, respectively in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: IBN slicing architecture and its layers, representing the NSS creation for different applications.

2) *Slice Intent Fulfillment*: This module deals with processing intents from their origin by an UE to their realization in the network, which encompasses intent translation into network resource requirements and slice intent creation. For example, the operation of spectrum, CPU processing, and TN capacity

required by a UE. To this aim, we create a slice intent template based on these pre-calculated network resource requirements, each imposed by particular UE intents, then we allocate the translated resources for each UE intent.

Accordingly, once modeling this module, we assume that each slice s contains a set of UEs/services with similar traffic behavior and the same QoS intents, and each UE is connected to AN a , where the UE association can be defined as:

$$\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} I_u^{r,s} \leq 1, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (3)$$

The binary variable $I_u^{r,s} \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether UE is connected to AN a .

We then calculate PRB requested by UE as $\rho_u^{a,s} = \frac{\lambda_u^s}{\eta_u^{a,s}}$ and instantiate an slice for each service s . Hence, the overall PRB needed by all connected UEs from various slices must not exceed the total available PRB in the AN a :

$$\rho^a \geq \sum_{(s,u) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} I_u^{a,s} \cdot \rho_u^{a,s}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (4)$$

TN Routing Requirements. The next UE intent that needs to be translated is TN routing requirements where, indeed, the network that delivers traffic towards UEs over path $p \in \mathcal{P}^r$ traversing from CN to AN a . All possible paths between AN a and CN are depicted by \mathcal{P}^a .

Therefore, the traffic supported by AN a through path p can be represented as t_p^a :

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^a} t_p^a = \sum_{(s,u) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} \lambda_u^s \cdot I_u^{a,s} \quad (5)$$

When determining routing selections, the link capacity should be respected:

$$\sum_{(a,s,p) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{P}^a} t_p^a \cdot J_{i,j}^p \leq \omega_{i,j}, \forall j \neq i \in \mathcal{N}, \forall s \neq 1 \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (6)$$

The constraint (6) specifies that the flow between AN a to CN is limited by the link capacity, denoted by $\omega_{i,j}$ (b/s). The indicator parameter $J_{i,j}^p \in \{0, 1\}$ indicates whether path p includes link $l_{i,j}$.

Objective. The goal of the MNO is maximizing the satisfaction of service intents that respects the network resource constraints. As the satisfaction of services is connected to the achieved throughput, hence, the objective function is translated to the maximization of the network throughput as defined in [20]:

$$O(I_u^{a,s}, t_p^a) = \sum_{(a,s,u) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{U}} \lambda_u^s \cdot I_u^{a,s} \quad (7)$$

After modeling the network resource constraints and creating slices for different services, we can put the above constraints together, and introduce the mathematical problem $\mathbb{P}1$, as:

$$\begin{array}{l}
\mathbb{P}1: \max_{I,t} O(I,t) \\
\text{s.t:} \\
(3)-(6) \\
I_u^{a,s} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall a \in \mathcal{A}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}
\end{array} \quad (8)$$

Constraint (8) represents the binary variables.

The problem $\mathbb{P}1$ is aimed to maximize satisfaction of services subject to the network resource constraints. However, each service may have different intent expectations, and each intent expectation may introduce multiple expectation targets, where this has not been taken into account in $\mathbb{P}1$. The intent expectation and expectation targets could be agreed between service owner and MNO as SLA agreement/objective for each particular slice, where MNO needs to address and fulfill the SLAs of each slice, named as *slice intent assurance*. To this end, in the next subsection, we discuss how these SLAs are modeled and respective solutions for the SLA violations are provided.

3) *Slice Intent Assurance*: The operations deal with ensuring that the network actually complies with the desired intent of the slice once it has been fulfilled. This phase can be checked with a slice intent feasibility Check; that is to check whether the SLA constraint/objective of a particular slice holds for each intent. In addition, MNO may create slice intents containing two or more intent expectations, and each intent expectation may contain multiple expectation targets, which may cause conflicts among different slice intents. Accordingly, the slice intent conflict should be detected and notified the conflict status if any, where this phase is named as *slice intent closed-loop monitoring and validation*. The conflict status may return *infeasible solution* due to a lack of network resources and which distinct slice intent belonging to the same or different slice caused this conflict. Finally, based on the intent status, the best policy could be assigned *e.g.*, in case of existing conflict the threshold in the SLA objective of a particular slice needs to be relaxed to mitigate and fulfill the SLA of another slice which has higher priority. Here, we deal with intent conflicts among different slices, aiming to meet their expectation targets as contracted SLA objectives.

Slice Intent Closed-Loop Monitoring and Validation.

We aim to model constraints for slice Intent closed-loop monitoring and validation, where we define slice intent Key Performance Indicator (KPI) scores as quantifiable metrics to evaluate the performance and effectiveness of each network slice in meeting specific service requirements and SLA objectives, which is tailored to the unique characteristics and priorities of each slice.

As defined in 3GPP [21], we consider slice capacity which refers to the maximum number of UEs/services to be served in that slice as KPIs to monitor and evaluate their performance, thus, providing relevant solutions. Accordingly, the slice intent KPI score is used to calculate the total served UEs per slice.

$$K^s = \left(\frac{\sum_{(a,u) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{U}} I_u^{a,s}}{n^s} \right), \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (9)$$

where n^s represents the total number of UEs candidates for slice s , while we have a variable $I_u^{a,s}$ indicating that candidate UEs are served in the network.

After monitoring and evaluating the performance of each slice based on the slice intent KPI scores, it is now necessary to provide solutions, such as setting thresholds for critical KPIs to address various QoS requirements in the intent profile. Indeed we incorporate intent expectation and its corresponding expectation targets into the network as contracted SLA objectives to satisfy their targets. The metric under consideration is the quantity of the particular slice that has been served and satisfied. This could be defined in terms of intent expectation targets and forced to establish a minimum percentage of services as SLA objectives, as well as a threshold for each slice.

$$\sum_{(a,u) \in \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{U}} I_u^{a,s} \geq \tau_1^s \cdot n^s, \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \quad (10)$$

where $\tau_1^s \in [0, 1]$ stands for the minimum proportion of UEs with service type s that must be served with the required QoS and n^s is the total number of UEs with service type s . Thus, the minimum number of UEs that should meet the required QoS is $\tau_1^s \cdot n^s$.

Problem $\mathbb{P}2$. To efficiently take intent of different and distinctive services/UEs into account, MNO may need to adapt its resources tailored to meet UEs intent expectation and corresponding expectation targets by imposing customized SLA objectives per slice. Hence, we extend the previous optimization framework ($\mathbb{P}1$) and include the constraints of contracted SLAs per slice mentioned above, and define $\mathbb{P}2$, where it implements a closed-loop evaluation to fulfill the intent requirements and prioritize the most important slices when there are no sufficient network resources for all slice intents.

$$\begin{array}{l}
\mathbb{P}2: \max_{I,t} O(I,t) \\
\text{s.t:} \\
(3)-(6), (9)-(10).
\end{array}$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We study a network scenario composed of a single CN connected to a set of ANs $A = 8$, where we assume that AN locations are distributed randomly with the ranges of 10 to 1000 /km to CN. We consider $s = 1$ for uRLLC with $\lambda_u^1 = 5$ Mb/s, $s = 2$ for mMTC with $\lambda_u^2 = 1$ Mb/s, and finally $s = 3$ for eMBB with $\lambda_u^3 = 20$ Mb/s [18], [22]. The number of UEs is fixed to 1000 UEs where 30%, 60%, and 10% are set to uRLLC, mMTC, and eMBB, respectively.

The optimization model was developed and solved using IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimization Studio [23]. The optimal

solution was obtained in a matter of seconds using a Core i7-1365U CPU processor and 32 GB of RAM for the investigated scenarios.

We illustrate the results of our numerical analysis in Fig. 2 to explore the insights of slice capacity, representing the maximum number of UEs/services to be served per slice and detect the slice intent conflicts. According to this figure, the slice capacity is improving with the increase in the TN capacity, and when $\omega_{i,j} \geq 2500$ almost all slices are fully satisfied. However, we observe that the slice intent conflicts happen when we have scarce resources in TN capacity *i.e.*, $\omega_{i,j} = 500$ to 2000 Mb/s. MNOs need to carefully explore the closed-loop evaluation in this case where there are network resource limitations to satisfy intents of slices. The potential solution is to prioritize those slices that are more important in terms of their QoS intents and must meet at least the agreed SLA objectives. Accordingly, we explore this potential solution in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2: Slice Capacity (%) w.r.t TN Capacity

Considering the performance we observed in Fig. 2, it is evident that uRLLC and eMBB slices have more tight QoS intents, however, these slices are the last to be served when $\omega_{i,j} = 500$ to 2000 Mb/s. Hence, in order to ensure that these slices are prioritized and meet their stringent requirements, we investigate the impact of enforcing the SLA objectives (%) on their capacity performance and that of the other slices.

In Fig. 3, we analyze the performance of slice capacity (%) once the minimum agreed SLA for the uRLLC slice has been enforced. It can be seen that the uRLLC slice capacity is enhanced by increasing the SLA objectives (%) as expected to fulfill the QoS intent requirements. However, this approach causes conflicts and violates the performance of other slices. For example, when $\omega_{i,j} = 1000$ Mb/s, the slice capacity of mMTC and eMBB is degraded once uRLLC SLA objectives (%) are increased. Note that it is not always feasible to achieve the agreed SLA objective, for example, when $\omega_{i,j} = 500$ Mb/s and when we set the uRLLC SLA objective to 100% for $\omega_{i,j} = 1000$ to 2000 Mb/s, the solution becomes infeasible due to the limitation of resources.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented an optimization approach for an IBN slicing framework to identify slice intent conflicts

by closed-loop evaluation and monitoring. This framework jointly solves the problem of slice intent conflict detection and resolution by formulation of an intent life-cycle optimization problem to handle the existing slice intent conflicts. We analyze the slice capacity of each slice to identify existing slice intent conflicts and evaluate the impact of implementing the agreed SLA objectives (%) for the slices with higher priority to be addressed. According to our results, this approach satisfies the slices with agreed SLA objective while violates the performance of other slices.

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Fig. 3: Slice Capacity (%) w.r.t TN Capacity

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